

Training programs and their effectiveness in improving receptive language skills among hearing-impaired children

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Abstract:-

This study aimed to identify the effectiveness of a training program to improve receptive language skills among hearing-impaired children, with a sample of (10) visitors to the Qalam Al-Hur Center for the Treatment and Education of People with Special Needs in Sabratha, from the age group (6-10) years. The study also used the curriculum. To achieve its objectives, the study also used a scale to measure receptive language skills and a training program as a tool for collecting data and information. The study also used a number of statistical methods, including the arithmetic mean, standard deviation, relative weight, t-test, Alpha-Cronbach reliability coefficient, Pearson correlation coefficient, and Reliability by the split-half method. The results of this study resulted in the presence of statistically significant differences in the level of responses of the study sample members at the level of (0.01) between the pre- and post-measurement of the receptive language skills test in favor of the post-measurement. It also resulted in the presence of statistically significant differences in the level of The responses of the study sample members, which are attributed to the gender variable (males/females) in favor of females. It also resulted in no statistically significant differences in the level of the study sample members' responses at the level of (0.01) between the post and follow-up measurement after a month of applying the program to the skills test. Receptive language, which indicates the effectiveness of the training program followed in this study in improving the receptive language skills of hearing-impaired children.

Keywords:-

Training programs - receptive language skills - hearing impaired.

Introduction to the study:

Anyone who examines the literature on special education will find that the category of the hearing-impaired suffers from many problems, some of which are related to the nature of the disability and some of which are related to the environmental factors surrounding the hearing-impaired person. Depriving the hearing-impaired person of the sense of hearing makes him vulnerable to many problems (Al-Person, 1992). These problems include the absence of speech and language in the individual, which negatively affected his communication and interaction with others and with those around him. Hearing disability negatively affects all aspects of linguistic development, and without organized and intensive training, people with hearing disabilities will not develop natural aspects of linguistic development. This is due to the absence of Auditory feedback when sounds are made, and not receiving sufficient linguistic reinforcement from others. In the event that they acquire linguistic skills, their language is characterized by not being as rich as the language of others, and with limited experience.

Their words are characterized by being centered around the concrete, and their sentences are shorter and less complex. As for their speech, it seems slow and low-pitched. Unusual (Al-Khatib, 1998, p. 85). The study of linguistic development began in the middle of the eighteenth century, when Tiedemann began in Germany to publish his studies in which he followed his son from the age of six months to three.

Then studies on this subject increased and the number of researchers increased. Those who were interested in studying linguistic development because it represents a basic aspect of a child's development, which is largely relied upon to measure the extent of growth in other aspects of a child's life, such as mental, emotional, and social development (Majid, 2009, p. 206). The child's linguistic development is considered to be of great importance. Because it helps

him meet his needs, express his thoughts and feelings, and also helps him interact and integrate (Roulstone, s, 2002, p: 30). The process of speech production is a process in which the speaker tries to achieve a series of goals that are compatible with the speech sounds that he is trying to produce, and it is based on two organs.

They are essential in the child. The first is the tongue, which is the speaking organ in production during the child's speech, and the second is the ear, which is the hearing organ that represents the source of speech perception during the speech of others. Hence, a correlation was found between speech perception and speech production (barnaucl.m, Schwartz's, et. al, 2019, p:2) The American Speech-Hearing Association said that the hearing impaired have great difficulty in developing and producing speech because part of the hearing is lost, which is the factor most relevant to the development and production of speech. However, modern technology, innovative hearing aids, and hearing aids, Early intervention programs play a crucial role in the development and production of speech for hearing-impaired children.

Thanks to early intervention, these children begin to produce speech more naturally and at a faster rate. However, if hearing loss occurs at an early stage, that is, at the time of the child's language and speech development, this growth stops, and the The child has gained the advantage of understanding some normal experiences related to language and speech, which are not available to the child who was born deaf. However, these experiences gradually disappear if the child is very young, and after a while he becomes equal to the child who was born deaf.

Accordingly, there is a major problem in The child's psychological, intellectual, social, and educational progress will occur when the hearing loss is significant and before the age of five. The older the age at which the hearing impairment occurs, the greater and more beneficial

the experiences related to language and speech. There is a group that becomes afflicted with hearing impairment at a later age due to an accident or illness. Here, the condition of hearing disability has a significant impact on their psychological, social and intellectual development (Al-Saratawi, et al., 2000, p. 171). Also, although the hearing-impaired child is born with his speech apparatus intact and complete, he cannot produce speech easily, as The process of producing speech is an extremely complex process, as it requires a period of time during which the child is exposed to the voices of speakers around him and then imitates them.

That is, the child learns to speak through the sense of hearing. Therefore, if there is an imbalance in the sense of hearing that prevents him from hearing some speech sounds, the child cannot He can produce these sounds, and since speech production is a verbal behavior that is acquired through learning by imitation and imitation, just like other behaviors that are learned by imitating others' behaviors, the child's hearing system must be intact to facilitate the process of verbal imitation, and since hearing loss reduces the child's ability To recognize different speech sounds, which are considered the basis for understanding language and verbal speech, which results in difficulty imitating this verbal speech among others. al, 2019, p: 2), barnaucl, m, schwartz) Therefore, many researchers and those interested in this aspect have devoted themselves to studying it and studying how to develop the sense of hearing and improve the aspect of speech and language in the individual, which has a positive impact on the individual's life, and among those methods used is the use of Rehabilitation programs, and based on the observations and information that the researcher settled on, all of which supported the importance of this study, the researcher conducted this study to shed more light on the deaf and hard of hearing category first, and to identify the effectiveness of training programs to improve the receptive language skills of

hearing-impaired children in an attempt to To alleviate the suffering of this group and try to integrate them into society.

Study problem:

The deaf group is considered one of the groups of people with special needs who are most sensitive and in need of the help of other people, due to the absence of the sense of hearing, which has hindered them from communicating with members of their community. Therefore, many people interested in this group have turned to researching the possibility of improving communication among this group by improving their speech and language. By subjecting them to a number of rehabilitation programs so that they can overcome this wall created by this disability, as language is the cornerstone of an individual's communication with others and with his surrounding environment. Therefore, the researcher in this study tried to investigate the feasibility of the effectiveness of training programs in improving skills. Receptive language among hearing-impaired children at the Al-Qalam Al-Hur Center for the Treatment and Education of People with Special Needs in Sabratha, following the approach of those who came before us and in continuation of their scientific journey and their role in trying to alleviate the suffering of our children from this group.

Importance of the study:

The importance of the current study arises in several points, which can be explained as follows:

- 1- The study is useful in monitoring the effectiveness of training programs to improve receptive language skills among a sample of hearing-impaired students who attend the Al-Qalam Al-Hur Center for the Treatment and Education of People with Special Needs in Sabratha.
- 2-Originality of the study, as this study is considered one of the few studies, if not the first, in the local environment that studies the

effectiveness of training programs to improve receptive language skills among hearing-impaired children.

3- This study is a scientific contribution to the development of services provided to the hearing disabled, especially in academic and social terms.

4-Reaching results on the basis of which a number of recommendations and proposals can be made that may help specialists in the field of hearing disability to advance this group academically and socially.

5-The study may contribute to revealing the gaps that exist in the education and rehabilitation program for people with hearing disabilities, especially in the language aspect, in order to avoid them in the future and develop solutions to eliminate them.

Study objectives:

In this study, the researcher attempts to achieve the following objectives:

1-Identify the effectiveness of training programs to improve receptive language skills among a number of visitors to the Qalam Al-Hur Center for the Treatment and Education of People with Special Needs.

2-Detecting differences in the level of responses of study sample members due to the gender variable (males/females).

Study hypotheses:

The researcher seeks to verify the validity of the following study hypotheses:

1-There are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.01) between the the pre- and post-measurement of the receptive language skills test in favor of the post-measurement.

2-There are statistically significant differences in the level of responses of the study sample members, which are attributed to the gender variable (males/females) in favor of females.

3-There are no statistically significant differences at the level of (0.01) between the post and follow-up measurements one month after implementing the program in testing receptive language skills for hearing-impaired children.

Limitations of the study:

:The limitations of the study are

1-**Objective limit:** - which is to study the effectiveness of training programs to improve receptive language skills among hearing-impaired children who attend the Qalam Al-Hur Center for the treatment and education of people with special needs in Sabratha.

2-**The spatial limit:** - which is represented by the Al-Qalam Al-Hur Center for the Treatment and Education of People with Special Needs in Sabratha.

3-**Time limit:** This study was conducted in the year 2024 AD

4-**The human limit:** - which is represented by a number of hearing-impaired students attending the Al-Qalam Al-Hur Center for the Treatment and Education of People with Special Needs in Sabratha, with a number of (10)students.

Previous studies:

Among these studies are the following:

1-**Khalil's study (2005):** entitled The impact of a remedial language program on developing receptive language skills in children with language disorders. The study aimed to develop a remedial language program and identify its effectiveness in developing receptive language

skills in children with language disorders, with a sample of (60) male and female children, aged between (5-6) years. The study used the receptive language scale. The results of the study concluded that the therapeutic language program was effective in developing receptive language skills in children with language disorders.

2-Abu Shaaban's study (2010): entitled The effectiveness of play therapy in language development in linguistically disturbed children. The study aimed to find out the effectiveness of play therapy in language development in linguistically disturbed children, with a sample of (16) male and female children whose ages ranged between (4- 6) years of those who suffer from linguistic disorder. The study used the linguistic comprehension measure and the counseling program based on play therapy. The results of the study found that there were statistically significant differences in the average scores of linguistic disorder according to the multiple measurements (pre, post, and follow-up) in the linguistic comprehension test among students. Children with linguistic disorders.

3-Study by Alimat and Al-Fayez (2012): entitled The Impact of a Linguistic Training Program to Develop Receptive Language Skills among Pre-School Children with Language Disorders in a Jordanian Sample. The study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of a linguistic training program to develop receptive language skills among pre-school children with language disorders. Linguistic disorders in a Jordanian sample, with a sample of (20) male and female children from the age group (3-5) years. The study used the receptive language measure and the language training programme. The results of the study showed that there were statistically significant differences between the experimental and control groups in developing language skills. Receptivity in favor of the experimental group.

4-Abu Qura’s study (2018): entitled “An enrichment program to treat delayed linguistic development in children and improve their social interaction.” The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of the enrichment program in treating delayed linguistic development in children and improving their social interaction, with a sample of (10) average male children. Their ages (4 years and 6 months), and the study used the Socioeconomic Level Scale, the Stanford-Binet Five-Piece Intelligence Scale, the Social Interaction Scale, the Linguistic Development Scale, and the enrichment program. The results of the study concluded that the enrichment program was effective in treating delayed linguistic development in children and improving Their social interaction.

Commenting on previous studies and comparing them to the current study:

Almost all previous studies agreed in their goals, tools, and results. All of these studies agreed on the importance of language in humans and the extent of its absence’s impact on the individual’s life at all levels. All studies also proved the effectiveness of all training programs in improving the language skills of children of all ages. Programs, how to prepare them, and the tools used in them.

Benefits from previous studies:

It is possible to summarize what the researcher has benefited from previous studies in the following points:

1-The researcher benefited from previous studies in obtaining information of scientific value, and it is considered a scientific basis against which the researcher can measure his information.

2-Through these studies, the researcher has the ability to know how other researchers deal with this topic, and thus the researcher is able to

reach the gaps that they did not talk about, and he talks about them as a scientific precedent and adds new information.

3-The researcher benefited from these studies in knowing the general structure of the research and getting to know closely how the research is written in order and its complete elements, and what each of these elements is.

4-The study was based on previous studies in determining the starting point and starting point for his study. He stopped at the matters on which those studies depended and then continued and added new information to them.

5-The presence of many previous studies confirms the importance of the topic that the researcher dealt with in his current study, thus convincing the reader of this importance and increasing the attraction of readers. Through the survey and intellectual nourishment that the researcher took from these studies, he was able to determine the elements of his study, or rather determine the hypotheses and variables that will be based on them. His study.

6-Previous studies were basic sources of information for the researcher. Through these studies, the researcher extracted a lot of information, and the researcher also conducted many cognitive processes such as discussions, analyses, and comparisons through these studies.

7-Previous studies do not only benefit the researcher and the study, but they also benefit the reader, and perhaps this aspect has not been paid attention to by many, but those who think about it will find that this benefit is seriously felt by the reader, whether the reader notices it or not, for one of them is that the reader Through the presence of information extracted from these studies, he finds diversity in presentation, and finds before him a discussion and dialogue template

between researchers, where each study represents the point of view of its author, and this makes the reader integrate with what he reads, continue reading, and benefit from the information widely. Likewise, when the reader finds analyses, Through these studies, the reader can understand the approach of the researcher's writer and anticipate the results that the researcher will reach through his treatment of previous studies. Also, the reader's careful consideration of the information quoted from previous studies gives him the ability to Distinguish many of the strengths and weaknesses of the study that he reads. These studies in general can be considered material that presents many aspects of the subject of study to the reader. It can also be said that these studies benefit the reader in that they often have a historical presentation, so the reader learns about the nature of the study. The topic over different dates.

Study procedures:

Study methodology: To verify the validity of the study hypotheses, the researcher used the experimental method as the appropriate method for such studies.

Study population: The study population consists of all students who attend the Qalam Al-Hur Center for the treatment and education of people with special needs in Sabratha.

Study sample: - It was selected through the researcher's communication with a number of children with hearing disabilities from the age group (6-10) years at the Qalam Al-Hur Center for the Treatment and Education of People with Special Needs in Sabratha. The sample was selected randomly from the study population, and is represented in:

1-**The exploratory sample:** It includes a number of (5) hearing-impaired children from the age group (6-10) years who attend the Al-Qalam Al-Hur Center for the treatment and education of people with special needs in Sabratha.

Table (1) shows the sample of the survey study

Number distributed	Exploratory Sample
3	Males
2	Females
5	Total Number

2-The actual sample: - It includes a number of (10) hearing-impaired children from the age group (6-10) years who attend the Al-Qalam Al-Hur Center for the treatment and education of people with special needs in Sabratha.

Table No. (2) shows the distribution of the actual study sample according to the gender variable

Percentage	Number	Actual Sample
%50	5	Males
%50	5	Females
%100	10	Total Number

Study tool:

The study tool is:

1-Language scale: (prepared by the researcher)

Objective of the scale: The scale aims to measure children's performance at receptive language levels on the one hand, and diagnose linguistic delay in children on the other hand.

Description of the scale: This scale consists of (20) items, and measures the child's ability to understand spoken words. The child is

asked to answer a set of questions. The examiner is given one score for each correct answer. A high score on this scale indicates a high level of the child's ability. On understanding spoken words, while a low score indicates a child's low ability to understand spoken words.

2-A training program (prepared by the researcher) to develop and improve the language skills of hearing-impaired children: The program consists of (90) sessions, and the program consists of three stages:

1-The first stage (the introductory stage): This means an introduction session between the researcher and the members of the study sample. During this session, the door to acquaintance is opened between the members of the study sample and the researcher. Also, during this session, the receptive language skills test is applied to the members of the study sample, where This stage takes (3) sessions. During these three sessions, hearing-impaired students are introduced to the program, its objectives, and its general rules. Each session lasts (120) minutes.

2-The second stage: It also consists of (4) stages, which are:

A-The first stage: This stage consists of (21) sessions. This stage aims to teach the child how to recognize names. This stage takes (42) hours, with a number of (21) sessions.

B-The second stage: This stage includes (21) sessions, for (42) hours, during which the child is trained to recognize verbs.

3-The third stage: This stage includes (21) sessions with (42) hours, as the researcher seeks in this stage to train the child to recognize how to compose sentences of various types. This axis included all the linguistic aspects that cannot be separated from each other. In receptive language, some of them are:

1-The linguistic form includes the phonetic aspect, the grammatical aspect, and the morphological aspect.

2-The semantics of words, which is the aspect that is concerned with the meanings of words, vocabulary, and sentences.

4-The fourth stage: This stage includes (21) sessions for (42) hours, as these sessions aim to introduce the child to the complete language in terms of its form and what it signifies, because that determines how this language is used, and because of the difficulty of separating some of these aspects from Others: When dealing with receptive language, a set of general axes were taken, namely: forming special sentences and training children to absorb them, understand their meanings, and respond to them correctly. This group of linguistic structures was divided into two main parts:

1-Limited-purpose sentences: In this section, children were trained on groups of sentences, and each group of these sentences was assigned a general goal that brings them together, even if they lead to more than one goal, but the goal of setting a general goal is to maintain the unity of training, and ease of measuring achievements. The child in order to know the extent to which the child has accomplished the task required of him. Among these linguistic groups are the following: sentences that indicate spatial conditions (above, below, in front of), sentences that include numerical skills (counting skill, addition skill), and sentences that include simple adjectives (a clean boy). Sentences that include compound adjectives (a black cat with a white tail), verbal nouns (he broke the glass, or Samer broke the glass), and sentences that include pronouns (your mother ate with you, your brother played with them).

2-Sentences of the sequence of events: This part of the sentences aims to develop the child's skill in being able to comprehend narrative narratives, understand the formation of sentences, and how to place linguistic links between the parts of a single sentence correctly and correctly, in order to ultimately reach a sound, integrated language that facilitates the process of linguistic communication between people. The child and his society, and because the subject of the study focuses on the receptive part of language, the child is required to understand this narrative sequence of events in each story presented to him, and he is not asked to narrate the story verbally, but rather he is asked to arrange

the pictures according to the correct sequence of events in the story, as he is asked to He can choose the picture that describes an event determined by the speech therapist, and so on until the desired goal of this part of the training is achieved.

3-The third stage: Completing the program, and measuring receptive language skills by applying the receptive language skills scale to the students in the study sample to ensure the effectiveness of the program. In the closing session, in-kind gifts, candy, and chocolate are distributed to the students, and after a month has passed since the completion of the training programs, the training programs are completed. Apply the receptive language skills scale again to ensure the continued effectiveness of the training program, with (3) sessions of (6) hours.

Researcher work steps:

They are:

A-Choosing a study sample.

B-The researcher applied the receptive language skills test to the study sample members.

C-Implementing the study program in its group sessions according to a set of techniques and methods that help children improve their receptive language skills.

D-Applying the receptive language skills test as a post-test again on the children in the study sample after completing the training program sessions. One month after completing the program, the researcher reapplied the receptive language skills measure again to the children in the study sample to see the extent of its continued effectiveness.

Validity and reliability of the study tool:

It consists of:

1-The honesty of the arbitrators: The measure of receptive language skills and the training program for developing those skills prepared by the researcher were presented to a number of arbitrators with

specialization and experience to express their opinion to a number of (5) arbitrators, and then their opinions were taken into account.

2-Internal consistency validity: The scale was applied to an exploratory sample of (5) hearing-impaired children, and the Pearson correlation coefficient was used to calculate the extent to which each statement relates to the study tool. The results were as follows:

Table No. (3) shows the extent to which each statement relates to the scale using the Pearson correlation coefficient

Pearson correlation coefficient	Scale Paragraphs
0.857	20

Through the results of the previous table, we found that the correlation coefficients of the statements with the scale they follow were all statistically significant at the significance level (0.01), which confirms that all statements in the questionnaire have a high degree of internal validity.

Stability of the study tool:

To calculate the reliability of the scale, the following were used:

1-Alpha-Cronbach reliability coefficient: - The Alpha-Cronbach reliability coefficient was used to calculate the reliability of the scale, using the statistical program (SPSS) for the data obtained from the exploratory sample, as shown in the following table:

Table No. (4) shows the calculation of the stability of the scale using the Fakronbach stability coefficient

Avakronbach's coefficient	Scale Paragraphs
0.866	20

From the results of the previous table, we can say that the scale has a high degree of reliability.

2-Using the half-split method: - The scale statements were divided into two halves, the odd statements versus the even statements, and the Pearson correlation coefficient was used to calculate the extent of the correlation between the two halves. The length was adjusted by the Cyberman and Brown coefficient, and by the Getman calculation coefficient, the results were as follows:

Table No. (5) shows the calculation of the stability of the scale using the halving method

Spearman and Brown Laboratories	Jetman coefficient	Pearson correlation coefficient	Scale Paragraphs
0.795	0.775	0.857	20

It is clear from the previous table that the reliability coefficients of the scale have a high degree of stability.

Study results:

Results of the first hypothesis:

Which states: There are statistically significant differences at the level of (0.01) between the pre- and post-measurements of the receptive language skills test in favor of the post-measurement. To confirm the validity of this hypothesis, the researcher used a number of statistical methods to confirm the validity of this hypothesis, and the results were as follows:

Table No. (6) shows the use of a number of statistical methods to determine the differences in the level of responses of the study sample members on the pre and post measurement to test receptive language skills

Significance level	Degree of freedom	T value	Standard Deviation	Arithmetic mean	Measurement	Scale Paragraphs
0.01	81	19.9	1.46	9.91	Pre-application	20
			3.05	17.70	Post-application	

Through the results obtained from the previous table, we notice that there are statistically significant differences between the pre- and post-measurement of the receptive language skills test in favor of the post-measurement. The researcher attributes this to the effectiveness of the training program to improve the receptive language skills of the study sample members, as the study sample members' scores on the appreciation test increased. Self-measurement after applying the program.

Results of the second hypothesis:

Which states: There are statistically significant differences in the level of responses of the study sample members, which are attributed to the

gender variable (males/females) in favor of females. To confirm the validity of this hypothesis, the researcher used a number of statistical methods to verify the validity of this hypothesis, and the results were as follows:

Table No. (7) shows the use of a number of statistical methods to determine the differences in the level of responses of the study sample members, which are attributed to the gender variable

Significance level	Degree of freedom	T value	Standard Deviation	Arithmetic mean	Gender	Scale Paragraphs
0.01	66	2.88	4.19	6.82	Males	20
			2.12	8.89	Females	

It is clear from the results obtained from the previous table that there are statistically significant differences in the level of responses of the study sample members, which are attributed to the gender variable (males/females), in favor of females. This is due from the researcher's point of view because females are more capable of acquiring communication skills and more capable of learning pronunciation. Letters and learning to speak compared to males, due to their nature and because they are more communicative and interactive with others than males.

Results of the third hypothesis:

Which states: There are no statistically significant differences at the level of (0.01) between the post and follow-up measurements after a month of applying the program in testing receptive language skills. To confirm the validity of this hypothesis, the researcher used a number of statistical methods to verify the validity of this hypothesis, and it was The results are as follows:

Table No. (8) shows the use of a number of statistical methods to determine the differences in the level of responses of the study sample members to the post and tracking measurement

State average	Application	Scale Paragraphs
9.8	Post-application	20
9.2	Tracking	

From the results obtained from the previous table, we note that there are no statistically significant differences between the post and follow-up measurements of the receptive language skills test. The researcher attributes this to the effectiveness of the training program followed to improve the receptive language skills of the study sample members, even after a period of time has passed since its application.

By comparing the results of this study with the results of previous studies, we find that the results of all studies resulted in the effectiveness of all the training programs used in these studies and the achievement of their objectives. Although these studies differ greatly in their objectives, results, and programs followed, we find that all previous studies and the researcher’s study have agreed on The importance of speech in humans and the extent of its absence’s impact on the individual’s life at all levels. It has proven the effectiveness of training programs in improving speech and communication among children with disabilities, regardless of the differences between these programs, the method of preparing them, and the tools used in them.

Conclusions:

The researcher concludes:

A-There are statistically significant differences in the level of responses of the study sample members at the level of (0.01) between the pre- and post-measurement of the receptive language skills test in favor of the post-measurement.

B-There are statistically significant differences in the level of responses of the study sample members, which are attributed to the gender variable (males/females) in favor of females.

C-There are no statistically significant differences in the level of responses of the study sample members at the level of (0.01) between the post and follow-up measurement after a month of applying the program to the receptive language skills test. This indicates the effectiveness of the training program followed in this study in improving skills. Receptive language in hearing-impaired children.

Recommendations

After the journey we went through in this study and going through its chapters, the:

researcher recommends. 1-Educating parents and specialists in particular about the importance of programs to improve and develop the child's language and the impact this has on his communication and interaction with others and his surrounding environment.

2-Early detection of language defects and problems.

3-Providing audiologists and speech-language pathologists in all educational institutions prepared and capable of diagnosing and treating cases of language disorders.

4-Training specialists on how to prepare language skills training programs and how to apply them to obtain the best results.

5-Paying attention to training programs to develop communication skills and adopting them as one of the most important ways to improve speech, language, and communication among hearing-impaired children.

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